

RELEVANCE OF MICROFINANCE CREDIT ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL-SCALE BUSINESSES IN CALABAR MUNICIPALITY OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Microfinance credit is considered a vital tool for the growth and survival of small-scale businesses globally. Consequently, this study evaluates its relevance to business performance of Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, using primary data collected through structured questionnaires. The study adopted simple percentages and chi-squares estimation techniques to summarize the data obtained and test the formulated hypotheses. The results revealed that credits from microfinance banks significantly affect profitability, employment creation capacity, and market expansion of small-scale businesses in the locality. Consequently, the study concludes that access to microfinance loans serves as a critical driver of small-scale business performance and growth in Calabar Municipality. Hence, recommended a less-stringent lending requirements improve loan accessibility for small-scale businesses; provision of enabling environment to enhance enterprise productivity and support job creation by the government; and enacting policies that encourage increased utilization of microfinance credit to improve the competitiveness and economic contributions of small-scale businesses in Cross River State.

Keywords: Microfinance Credit, Small-Scale Businesses, Profitability, Employment Generation, Business Expansion, Cross River State.

JEL Classification: G24, L2, L1, E2, L1, R5

1. INTRODUCTION

Small-scale businesses are recognized as catalysts in socio-economic development of countries. They are veritable channels of attaining macroeconomic objectives of improved employment level as well as the development of entrepreneurial skills, homegrown technology, moderating rural–urban migration, indigenous resource utilization, and poverty alleviation. Small-scale businesses are referred to as businesses that are owned and managed independently operating with relatively small capital outlays, small number of workers, and modest annual returns (SMEDAN & National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). They are common in both developing and developed economies because of their role in driving economic development in rural and urban areas. As a result, governments make persistent attempts in developing the sector in-charge of small-scale businesses in order to promote economic development by providing enabling environment for the prosperity of such businesses, and /or essential incentives for the sector’s growth (Etale & Light, 2021). Globally, small-scale businesses contribute over 50 per cent to gross domestic product (GDP) in developed countries. Most of the developed economies have recognized the role of small-scale businesses in industrial restructuring and went further to formulate and adopt national financial policies for the growth of small-scale businesses (Ikpor et al, 2017). But the tendency of small-scale businesses in driving the economy through job creation, investment expansion and increase

in output depends on their financial liquidity. Availability of fund helps the businesses to spread their investment nets thereby creating job, expanding output, profit margins as well as gaining market shares. However, the ability of small-scale businesses accomplishing the aforementioned goals is hampered by inadequate or nonavailability capital including stringent conditions on loans by financial agencies (Schneider, 2002). This position is further buttressed by Mambula (2002) who affirmed that small-scale businesses are often constrained by insufficient operating capital, high cost of borrowing and inaccessibility of funds resulting to their early death.

In Nigeria, government at various times established different financial agencies such as the National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) 1989, the merging of NERFUND and NIDB to Bank of Industry in 2001 to provide loan at interest rate of 10 percent to the industrial sector and small-scale businesses. In 2005, the Central Bank of Nigeria established Nigeria's first microfinance policy framework aimed at alleviating the financial needs of small and medium enterprises and ensure their viability. Also in 2024, the Nigerian Credit Corporation (CREDICORP) was established as a provider of wholesale funding and credit-guarantee support to banks, microfinance institutions and fintechs. The creation of the agency was targeted towards expansion of consumer credit, easing credit accessibility by working Nigerians and small businesses (Nigerian Consumer Credit Corporation, n.d.). The National Credit Guarantee Company Limited was as well established in May 29, 2025 to provide partial credit guarantees and de-risk lending for micro small and medium enterprises, small corporations and manufacturers. Hence, it was aimed at encouraging banks and financial institutions at large to extend loans to small-scale businesses (Nairametrics, 2025; NewsKobo, 2025).

Nonetheless, the contribution of microfinance loans to small-scale businesses seems inadequate considering their performance in terms of market share, employment, profitability and survival. For example, while small-scale businesses account for about 96 per cent of businesses and 84 per cent of employment in 2023, its contribution to Nigeria's gross domestic product was only 48 per cent. Also, in 2021, at least, 39,654,385 micro, small and medium enterprises operated in Nigeria and over 40 per cent failed as a result of inability to obtain finance and infrastructural deficit among others. It therefore, becomes pertinent to ask the following research questions: what impact does microfinance loan have on the profit margin of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality? Does microfinance loan influence the employment generating ability of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality? And, is the market shares of small-scale businesses associated with microfinance loans in Calabar Municipality of Cross River State? In order to provide answers to the research questions, the study broadly aims at evaluating the relevance of microfinance credit on the performance of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality. But on the specifics, it intends to examine the impact of microfinance loan on the profit margin of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality; investigate influence of microfinance loan on employment generating ability of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality; and to ascertain if market shares of small-scale businesses is associated with microfinance loans in Calabar Municipality of Cross River State of Nigeria. The study is reported in five broad sections. The first section introduces the study while the second section is the literature review. The methodology adopted by the study is described in the third section as the fourth section presents the results and discussion of findings. The concluding section consists of the conclusion and policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical literature

The financial constraint theory founded by Fazzari, Hubbard and Petersen (1988), provides explanations on why investment decision, growth and productivity of firms are been constrained due to their limitations in obtaining external finance. Consequently, they are prevented from exploring productive investment opportunities capable of yielding positive returns. The theory also noted that information asymmetry between lenders and borrowers place small firms in a disadvantaged position resulting in credit rationing or complete denial of loans. It further suggests that due to the limitations encountered by small businesses in accessing external loans, they rely on internal financing, exposing investment to the risk of fluctuations in internal cash flow.

On the other hand, Gurley and Shaw (1960) developed the financial intermediation theory which explains the intermediation role of financial institutions in bridging the gap between savers (surplus units) and the borrowers (deficit units). The theory was expanded later by scholars in finance and economic growth such as Levine (2005). The theory recognized the existence of people/businesses with excess funds who have preference for safe and liquid assets along with those who usually need long-term capital for investment. Hence, microfinance is perceived as a channel through which the two categories of people/businesses are linked, thereby promoting business performance, investment in addition to stimulating local economic growth.

2.2 Empirical literature

Literature abounds on the relationship between microfinance institutions and micro, small and medium enterprises, especially on funding of the latter. Gyimah (2024) studied the effect of microfinance products in forms of savings, loans, education and insurance on the performance of rural small businesses in Ghana. Perceiving business performance in terms of profitability and sales growth the study employed primary survey methodology and a regression analysis and found that microloans increased sales but not profits. Also, the result showed that micro-savings increased profitability rather than sales growth; insurance positively affected profit (but not sales growth); and lastly, education/training from MFIs increased both sales and profits. Hence, the study concluded that microfinance products matter, but effects differ by product non-credit services (education, insurance, savings) are important drivers of small business performance in rural Ghana; microcredit alone does not guarantee profit improvements. In a similar study, Kisaka and Mwewa (2014) examined the effects of micro-credit, micro-savings and training on SME growth in Kenya using quantitative survey, descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Like the study of Gyimah (2024), the result established that, micro-credit and training were positively associated with SME growth indicators (sales and employment); micro-savings also supported business stability while constraints included loan sizes and interest rates. The study therefore concluded that while the combination of microfinance credit, savings and training support SME growth in Machakos County, product design (affordable rates, adequate loan size) and training quality are important for stronger impacts. The findings of Gyimah (2024) as well as Kisaka and Mwewa (2014) corroborates the submission of Azzan (2021) in a similar study for Kenya. Also, the findings of Ibrahim and Sani (2024) on microfinance banking and smallholder rice farmers performance in Kaduna state of Nigeria supports the submission of Gyimah (2024) on the impact of microcredit and training on the performance. Bassey, Amoke and Oha (2025) explored a survey design to examine factors that determine the performance of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) with particular focus on the Southern Senatorial District of Cross River State. The study observed that while financial factors negatively and abysmally affect micro, small and medium

enterprises performance, the impact of human capital and socio-cultural factors were positive and significant. The study proposed easy accessibility of funds by MSMEs like Ibrahim and Sani (2024), business-friendly environment and new digital infrastructure as possible measures to be taken by the government to ensure optimal performance of MSMEs in the area. The study of Ukwuaba, *et al.* (2025) tried to evaluate the drivers of market participation dynamics of small-scale rice farmers within the South East of Nigeria. With the application of market participation index and Heckman's two-stage model, the study identified education among the drivers of market participation. Consequently, they recommended the integration of market-oriented training to enhance small-scale farmers capacity so as to make well-versed, appropriate and strategic decision making. In the same vein, Oloto and Oko (2025) identified the significance of entrepreneurship education in driving employment generation capacity in addition to stimulating long term economic growth in Nnewi, Nigeria.

In another development, Sarfo, Zhang, O'Kane & O'Kane (2024) investigated direct and mediated relationships between perceived value of microfinance, exploratory innovation and performance in developing countries using structural equation modelling as well as complementary qualitative insights. The result revealed that, perceived value of microfinance positively affects exploratory innovation; exploratory innovation strongly predicts SME performance; the direct effect of perceived value on SME performance becomes insignificant once exploratory innovation is included, that is, exploratory innovation fully mediates the relationship. Therefore, the study concluded that microfinance contributes to SME performance primarily by enabling exploratory innovation (new product/process actions) and suggested that microfinance institutions should design products and services that encourage innovative activity among borrowers. The study of Anata (2023) and Affandi (2024) in Indonesia, in related studies found that innovativeness in form of digital channels boost sales, profitability and growth of small and medium scale enterprises as established by Sarfo, Zhang, O'Kane & O'Kane (2024) and Murshid *et al.* (2022).

In a related study, Moussa (2020) evaluated the impact of microfinance credit from microfinance institutions on the financial performance of small and medium scale enterprises in North Lebanon. The result, like the outcome of a cross-country research by Kanga (2024) shows evidence of a positive association between microcredit access and several financial performance indicators, although sample size limits generalizability and context (economic conditions) mattered. Hence, the researcher concluded that Microcredit can positively affect SME financial performance, but effects are context-sensitive and small samples or unstable macro conditions limit inferences.

For Nigeria, Aderemi (2023) examined the effect of SMEs access to microfinance credit on business growth in Nigeria adopting a primary survey technique. The study found that most SMEs used microfinance for working capital and asset acquisition; 61.5% accessed microfinance in last year; respondents reported microfinance as critical for operations and expansion but identified high interest rates and limited loan sizes as constraints. As a result, the study concluded that Microfinance plays an important enabling role for Lagos small businesses improving liquidity and enabling assets, but high cost and access constraints limit potential performance gains. Conversely, Owolabi and Nasiru (2017) used Pearson's correlation to analyze the effect of SME credit and unemployment and poverty and also examined the effects of deposit money bank credit to SMEs on Nigerian economic growth. Using annual data from 1992 to 2015 and ordinary least squares regression. The result showed a negative, statistically significant relationship between SME credit and poverty, but an insignificant negative relationship between SME credit and unemployment. According to the results of Ordinary Least Squares regression, SME financing has

a negative and statistically significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Whereas the findings of Asor et al. (2016) on microfinance banks on small scale businesses in Calabar, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria descriptive research method revealed increased challenges of microfinance operations and the challenges of small-scale businesses. The outcome of the study while agreeing the findings of Gyimah (2024), Kisaka and Mwewa (2014) including Azzan (2021) disagrees with Owolabi and Nasiru (2017). Bassey, Ifere, Amoke and Ato (2025) also noted a number of challenges faced by small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. Adopting the ARDL estimation technique, the study observed that the number of commercial bank and rural branches influence small and scale enterprises outputs in Nigeria. Hence, the suggestion that the Central Bank of Nigeria should promote financial inclusion by expanding microfinance banks branches in rural areas via deepening its pressure on commercial banks with special directives.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical framework

This study is anchored on financial intermediation theory and the credit constraint theory. The intermediary role of financial institutions in fund mobilization from savers (surplus unit) to borrowers (deficit unit) is explained by the financial intermediation theory. In this context, microfinance banks provide loans to small-scale businesses who do not have access to formal banking system. As a result, they ease financial constraints and enable small-scale businesses to access working capital, invest productively and extend operations. This supports the presupposition that business performance is enhanced by improved access to credit (Gurley & Shaw, 1960; Levine, 2005). Similarly, the credit constrain theory also referred to as financial constraint theory provides explanation on limitations to growth and productivity of small-scale businesses due to inadequate access to external finance. It noted some of the constraints faces by small-scale businesses as high interest rate, collateral conditions including restricted lending relationship. But loans from microfinance institutions are designed to eliminate such constraints and help entrepreneurs to expand their outputs, sales as well as competitiveness (Fazzari, Hubbard, & Petersen, 1988).

3.2 Research design and study area

The study employed a quantitative descriptive survey research design. This design helps researchers to determine relationships between independent and dependent variables within a population according to Michael, Oparaku and Oparaku (2012). Calabar Municipality, is the the capital of Cross River State as well as the headquarters of the Municipal Government. From historical perspective, Calabar was the Southern Protectorate capital and later developed to one of the initial centres of local government administration in the previous Eastern Region. Geographically, the Municipality lies between latitude 4°15'–5°N and longitude 8°25'E. It is bounded by Odukpani Local Government Area to the north, the Great Kwa River to the northeast, and by Calabar River and Calabar South to the south. The approximate square kilometres covered by Calabar Municipality is 331.551 (Aye & Ekpe, 2018).

3.3 Population and sampling

The population of study consists of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) owners and operators of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality who currently access microfinance credit. The businesses are categorized under provision shops, food vendors, barber shops, Point of Sale (POS) operators and restaurants among others within Calabar Municipality. Their selection is because they represent the dominant forms of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality and constitute

the key beneficiaries of microfinance credit schemes targeted towards promoting business performance according to (Bassey, 2014).

The sample size was determined using the simplified formular of Yamane (1997) as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

As n represents sample size, N is the population size, while e is the precision level or margin of error (0.05). Using the formular, we have;

$$n = \frac{327}{1 + 327(0.05^2)} \approx 180 \text{ respondents}$$

The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to ensure a representative sampling as well as minimum sampling bias and in recognition of the heterogeneous nature of small-scale business activities in the area. The stratification was done base on business-size, type and location within Calabar Municipality. Calabar Municipality was divided into four stratum: Ikot Ansa, 8Miles, Etta Agbor and Big Qua Town because of the density of small-scale businesses within the various locations. The distribution of the population was Ikot Ansa = 90 businesses, 8Miles 90 businesses, Etta Agbor = 90 businesses and Big Qua Town = 67 business. Using the formular for each stratum, we have

$$\text{Sample}_{\text{stratum}} = \frac{\text{population}_{\text{stratum}}}{\text{total population}} \times \text{total sample}$$

$$\text{For Ikot Ansa: } \frac{90}{327} \times 180 = 49.54$$

$$8\text{Miles: } \frac{90}{327} \times 180 = 49.54$$

$$\text{Etta Agbor} = \frac{80}{327} \times 180 = 44.036$$

$$\text{Big Qua Town} = \frac{67}{327} \times 180 = 36.88$$

Thus, $49.54 + 49.54 + 44.036 + 36.88 = 179.996 \approx 180$ respondents.

The study employed structured questionnaire for data collection. The questionnaire is made up of 16 questions divided into three sections. Section A captured the demographic characteristics of the respondents, section B, socioeconomic features of the respondent and, Section C contained the impact of microfinance funding in the performance of small and medium scale enterprises. The questionnaire was personally administered to the respondents with the aid of three field assistance. In determining the reliability of the instrument used for the study, a pilot test exercise was carried out by the researcher on 20 respondents outside the study area for the purpose of establishing test-retest reliability. The respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire and then asked to complete it again after three weeks. The Cronbach's Alpha test was then computed for the two sets of responses for the reliability of the overall score. The high value of the Cronbach's Alpha test 0.78 indicated that the instrument is reliable.

The study employed simple percentages in analysing the demographic features of the respondents, socioeconomic characteristics of the respondent as well as the impact of microfinance loan on the performance of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality. Furthermore, Chi-Square (χ^2) Test was explored to test for significance for the stated hypotheses using the formula;

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where;

O_i = Observed frequency

E_i = Expected frequency

χ^2 = Chi-square

The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis if calculated chi-square value is greater than the critical value at 5 percent significant level, the null hypothesis is rejected indicating a significant relationship.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Out of the 180 questionnaires distributed to the respondents, only 168 were appropriately completed and returned, 5 were not returned while 7 were invalidated due to incomplete or inconsistent responses. Table 4.1 presents the summary of the responses on the effect of microfinance loan on profit margin of small-scale businesses as well as the Chi-squares result. The result shows that 50 (29.76%) respondents indicate that profit margin of their businesses has significantly increased due to microfinance loans. Whereas, a greater proportion of the respondents— 69 representing 41.07 percent, agreed that they have experienced moderate increase in their business profit margins, 32 (19.05%) and 17 (10.12%) of the respondents respectively responded no change and decrease in their profit margin due to microfinance loans. The pattern of response on the question suggests that microfinance loans have significant impact on the profit margins of small-scale businesses since about 70.83% of the respondents reported that their businesses have experienced increased profit due to microfinance loan. This result corroborates the hypothesis test indicated by the Chi-square test result on the table. With the chi-square calculated value of 36.14 and critical value of 7.815 at 3 degrees of freedom and five percent significance level. The hypothesis for this section demonstrates that the calculated value of the chi-square is greater than its critical value. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected which implies that the profit margin of small-scale businesses is significantly affected by microfinance loan in Calabar Municipality. While agreeing with the findings of Moussa (2020), the result contradicts the findings of Gyimah (2024) on effect of microfinance loan on profitability for Ghana. This finding demonstrates the importance of microfinance loans in boosting profit margins of small-scale business as indicated by a greater share of the respondents. With perceived positive impact of microfinance loans on the profitability of the businesses, small-scale businesses will be motivated to subscribe to microfinance banks loans in expanding and sustaining their businesses. If such trend continues, a great developmental transformation will be experienced within the locality as many will be lifted out of poverty as the growing unemployment rate in the state and country in particular will be reduced significantly.

Table 4.1: How has microfinance loan affected your business' profit margin?

Responses	Observed frequency (%)	Expected frequency	$\chi^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Increased significantly	50 (29.76%)	42	1.524
Increased moderately	69 (41.07)	42	17.357
No change	32 (19.05)	42	2.381
Decreased	17 (10.12)	42	14.881
			$\chi^2 = 36.143$

Source: Computation by the Author using responses from the questionnaires

Table 4.2 presents analysis of the responses for the second objective which is used to test the corresponding hypothesis on the effect of microfinance loan on employment generation capacity of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality. The description of the table portends that microfinance loan strengthens the ability of small-scale businesses in job creation within the study

area. This is assertion is supported by the affirmative response of over 70 percent of the respondents on the subject matter. Whereas 32 respondents which constitutes only 19 percent of the responses recognized that their employment capacity have not changed due to microfinance loans, 19 (11.3%) respondents accepted that a decline in their hiring ability owing to microfinance loan. The result from the response analysis conforms to the result of the hypothesis test also presented in Table 4.2. According to the result, microfinance loan exerts statistically significant impact on employment generation ability of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality at 5 percent level. This is premised on the fact that the value of the calculated chi-square statistic ($\chi^2 = 29.95$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.05$) which is greater than the critical value ($\chi^2_{critical} = 7.815$ ($df = 3, \alpha = 0.005$)) at the chosen level of significance. However, this result contradicts the findings of Owolabi and Nasiru (2017) on SMEs credit and unemployment in Nigeria, but related to the findings of Oloto and Oko (2025) on employment generating capability though driven by education not credit. The result implies that the state can leverage on microfinance loans to small-scale businesses to curb the rising rate of unemployment and its negative impact on the state economy and the country at large.

Table 4.2: How has microfinance loan affected your ability to hire more employees?

Responses	Observed Frequency/ Percentage	Expected frequency	$\chi^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Increased significantly	52 (30.95)	42	2.381
Increased moderately	65 (38.7)	42	12.595
No change	32 (19.0)	42	2.381
Decreased	19 (11.3)	42	12.595
Total	168		29.952

Source: Computation by the Author using responses from the questionnaires

Furthermore, responses on the impact of microfinance loan on the business market share of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality which is used in testing the third hypothesis is presented in Table 4.3. As shown on the table, the analyzed responses from the respondents portends that most of them agreed that the impact of microfinance loan on their business market shares is significant. However, about 19 per cent and 11.3 per cent of the responses representing an insignificant proportion of the respondents indicate that their business market shares either have not changed or decreased due to microfinance loan, respectively. Since the number or percentage of responses in favour of the impact of microfinance loan on business market share is moderately high, it suggests that indeed, microfinance loan has significantly affected market share of small-scale businesses in the area. This result is validated by the result of the chi-square test for the third null hypothesis. The calculated value of the chi-square statistic ($\chi^2 = 29.95$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.05$) exceeds the critical value ($\chi^2_{critical} = 7.815$) at 5 percent level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected signifying that microfinance loan promotes the business market share of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality. This finding supports the result of Affandi (2024) that microfinance spurs higher sales growth for small scale businesses, though with the combination of digital tools as also found by Anatan (2023) and Kisaka and Mwewa (2014). Nonetheless, it contrasted the findings of Basse, Amoke and Oba (2025) on the none significant effect of financial factors on the performance of micro, small and medium scale businesses in the Southern Senatorial District of Calabar.

Table 4.3: How has microfinance loan affected your business market share?

Responses	Observed Frequency/ Percentage	Expected frequency	$x^2 = \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$
Increased significantly	65 (38.7)	42	12.595
Increased moderately	52 (30.95)	42	2.381
No change	32 (19.0)	42	2.381
Decreased	19 (11.3)	42	12.595
Total	168		29.952

Source: Authors computation

Table 4.4: Summary of the Chi-square result

Hypothesis	χ^2 Calculated	Df	χ^2 Critical (0.05)	Decision
H ₁ (Profitability)	36.14	3	7.8.5	Reject H ₀
H ₂ (Employment)	29.95	3	7.815	Reject H ₀
H ₃ (growth)	29.95	3	7.815	Reject H ₀

Source: Authors computation

Table 4.4 summarizes the result of the tested hypotheses already explained. On the whole, the result revealed that microfinance credit significantly affects profitability, employment and growth of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality. This development contradicts the earlier stated null hypotheses of the study, as a result, the study rejects the null hypotheses and conclude that the performance of small-scale businesses is greatly affected by microfinance credits in Calabar Municipality of Cross River State.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study investigated the relevance of microfinance credits on the performance of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Employing a primary survey design and the Chi-square statistics, the study found that microfinance loan significantly affects the profit margin, employment generating ability and market share of small-scale businesses in the study area. Therefore, the study conclude that microfinance credits are critical in determining the performance of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality of Cross River State.

Base on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made: Since microfinance loans significantly affect the profit margin of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality, the financial authority should ensure ease in the conditions that militate against the accessibility of microfinance loans to by small-scale businesses to ensure their viability. This is because of its potentiality in promoting small-scale business investment, output and employment, hence, economic growth and development in the State. Also, given that microfinance loan has a significant influence on employment generating ability of small-scale businesses in Calabar Municipality, business-supporting environment should be created by the government. This will stimulate the operation of small-scale businesses and spur them to explore microfinance loans for expansion, hence, creating more jobs and reducing the growing unemployment and poverty rates

in the area. Also, since microfinance loans promotes small-scale business growth through their market shares, the Central Bank of Nigeria should enact policies that will promote the frequency of microfinance loan reception by small-scale businesses so as to further expand their market share, encourage competitiveness and output growth in the economy.

REFERENCES

- Aderemi, G. (2023). *The impact of microfinance on small business development in Lagos, Nigeria* (Master's thesis, University of Salford). Salford Business School. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381096332> The Impact of Microfinance on Small Business Development in Lagos Nigeria
- Affandi, Y., Ridhwan, M. M., Trinugroho, I., & Adiwibowo, D. H. (2024). Digital adoption, business performance, and financial literacy in ultra-micro, micro, and small enterprises in Indonesia. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 70, 102376.
- Anatan, L. & Nur (2023). Micro, small and medium enterprises' readiness for digital platforms in Indonesia. *Economies*, 11 (6), 156. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies11060156>
- Asor, A. E., Essien, M. E., & Ndiyo, N. (2016). *The impact of microfinance banks on small scale businesses in Cross River State: A case study of Calabar Metropolis*. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 4(1), 25–31. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.365436530>
- Aye, E. E., & Ekpe, A. E. (2018). *Geography and development of Cross River State*. Calabar: University of Calabar Press
- Azzan, K. S. (2021). Effect of micro-finance on financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Kwale County, Kenya. (Master's thesis, University of Nairobi). Faculty of Business and Management Science. Retrieved online at <file:///C:/Users/D%20R'%20%20M%20E%20R%20C%20Y/Downloads/c898a59e-0a32-4005-89ef-0a2c90d08c65-Khaliga%20%20Asallim%20Azzan%20-Project.pdf>.
- Bassey, E. B.; Ifere, E. O., Amoke, C. V. & Ato, I. N. (2025). Financial inclusion, microcredit and performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 214-228.
- Bassey, G. E. (2014). Microfinance and the performance of small-scale enterprises in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(7), 27–34.
- Bassey, O. E., Amoke, C. V. & Oha, A-E. E. (2025). Determinants of micro, small and medium enterprises performance in southern senatorial district of cross river state, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 128-147.
- Etale, L. M., & Light, O. B. (2021). An evaluation of the impact of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) development on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), 54-70.
- Fazzari, S. M., Hubbard, R. G., & Petersen, B. C. (1988). Financing constraints and corporate investment. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 1988(1), 141–206. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2534426>
- Gurley, J. G., & Shaw, E. S. (1960). *Money in a theory of finance*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution.
- Gyimah, P. (2024). Advancing rural entrepreneurship: Does microfinancing matter? *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 34(1), 77–95.
- Ibrahim, Y. A. & Sani, B. N. (2024). Impact of microfinance banking services on the performance of smallholder rice farmers in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(4), 46-55.

- Ikpor, R., Nnabu, B.E., & Itumo, O.S. (2017). Bank lending to small and medium scale enterprises and its implication on economic growth in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 22(12, 5), 14-28.
- Kanga, D. (2024). Financial sector development and microcredit to small firms: Evidence from emerging economies. *Journal of Economic Analysis and Policy*, 28(3), 185–198.
- Kisaka, S. E., & Mwewa, N. M. (2014). Effects of micro-credit, micro-savings and training on the growth of small and medium enterprises in Machakos County in Kenya. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(7), 43–49.
- Levine, R. (2005). Finance and growth: Theory and evidence. In P. Aghion & S. Durlauf (Eds.), *Handbook of Economic Growth (Vol. 1, pp. 865–934)*. Elsevier. The Working-Paper Version: NBER Working Paper 10766. DOI: 10.3386/w10766
- Mambula, C. (2002). Perceptions of SME growth constraints in Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 40(1), 58–65. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-627X.00029>
- Michael, M. C., Des-Oparaku, L. & Oparaku, D.C (2012). *Basic tools in research method and project writing*. Hornicorn Int'l.
- Moussa, F. (2020). Impact of microfinance loans on SMEs' performance in North Lebanon. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 21(5), 1457–1473. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2020.12893>
- Nairametrics. (2025, May 29). *Tinubu establishes Credit Guarantee Company with ₦100 billion initial capital, appoints board*. Retrieved from <https://nairametrics.com/2025/05/29/tinubu-establishes-credit-guarantee-company-with-n100-billion-initial-capital-appoints-board/> (Nairametrics)
- NewsKobo. (2025, July 4). *FG inaugurates National Credit Guarantee Company board to support MSME access to finance*. Retrieved from <https://newskobo.com/>
- Nigerian Consumer Credit Corporation. (n.d.). *About us*. Retrieved November 26, 2025. Retrieved from <https://www.credicorp.ng/about>
- Oloto, S. E. & Oko, U. K. (2025). Entrepreneurship education and employment creation in Nnewi, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 75-86.
- Owolabi, O. A., & Nasiru, A. (2017). Deposit money bank credit to small and medium enterprises, socio-economic performance and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 6(10), 1400–1417.
- Sarfo, C., Zhang, J. A., & O’Kane, C. (2024). Perceived value of microfinance and SME performance: Evidence from emerging markets. *International Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 31(2), 204–222.
- JSchneider, B. F. (2002). Africa’s aborted industrialization: Modernisation strategies impede organic industrial growth. *D+C Development and Cooperation*, (1), 15–17. Deutsche Stiftung für Internationale Entwicklung (DSE), Germany.
- SMEDAN, & National Bureau of Statistics. (2021). *SMEDAN and NBS collaborative survey: Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSME) national survey report*. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://smedan.gov.ng/smedan-and-nbs-msme-survey-report-2021/>
- Ukwuaba, I. C., Ibe, C. J., Onyekwe, C. N., Adebayo, O., Bamijoko, B., Ukwuaba, I. C., & Asogwa, C. A. (2025). What drives the market participation dynamics of small-scale rice farmers in southeast Nigeria? *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 10(3), 87–104.
- Yamane, T. (1997). *Statistics: An introductory analysis* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Harper & Row.